

SELECTED FINAL STUDIES

ID	Ref.	Title	Publication Year	Publication Type	What types of research have been presented?	What types of contribution have been presented?	What are the domains addressed in the studies?	How have the approaches been evaluated?
S1	[1]	Smart Contract Microservitization	2020	Conference	Proposal of solution	Model	Smart Contract	Experiment > 50%
S2	[16]	Enabling Enterprise Blockchain AppDev Teams	2017	Conference	Personal experience papers	Architecture	General	Not empirically evaluated
S3	[2]	BlendMAS: A BLockchain-ENabled Decentralized Microservices Architecture for Smart Public Safety	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Smart City	Experiment > 50%
S4	[17]	On the Design of a Blockchain-based Student Quality Assessment System	2020	Conference	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Education	Not empirically evaluated
S5	[18]	An Application Model that Leverages Microservice and Blockchain Technologies	2020	Conference	Proposal of solution	Model	Online Commerce/Marketplace	Not empirically evaluated
S6	[3]	MSChain: Blockchain based Decentralized Certificate Transparency for Microservices	2020	Conference	Proposal of solution	Architecture	General	Experiment > 50%
S7	[8]	Building a prototype based on Microservices and Blockchain technologies for notary's office: An academic experience report	2020	Conference	Personal experience papers	Lessons Learned	Notary's Office	Not empirically evaluated
S8	[19]	Improving Banking Transactions Using Blockchain Technology	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	System	Bank	Not empirically evaluated
S9	[20]	A Novel IoV Block-Streaming Service Awareness and Trusted Verification Scheme in 6G	2021	Journal	Proposal of solution	System	IoV	Experiment > 50%
S10	[21]	A Microservices Architecture for ADS-B Data Security using Blockchain	2020	Conference	Proposal of solution	Framework	Aviation Systems	Not empirically evaluated
S11	[22]	ITrade: A Blockchain-based, Self-Sovereign, and Scalable Marketplace for IoT Data Streams	2020	Symposium	Proposal of solution	Architecture	IoT	Experiment < 50%
S12	[23]	A Study of Lightweight DDDAS Architecture for Real-Time Public Safety Applications Through Hybrid Simulation	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	Framework	Smart City	Experiment < 50%
S13	[24]	Ethereum smart contracts as blockchain-oriented microservices	2018	Conference	Proposal of solution	Model	Smart Contract	Not empirically evaluated
S14	[25]	A Shared Blockchain Intelligent Public Protection Service Framework	2020	Journal	Proposal of solution	Framework	Smart City	Experiment < 50%

S15	[26]	Clinically-validated technologies for assisted living: The VINCI project	2021	Journal	Validation research	Architecture	Healthcare	Survey < 50%
S16	[6]	SaaS - Microservices-Based Scalable Smart Contract Architecture	2020	Symposium	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Smart Contract	Experiment > 50%
S17	[27]	Smart Contracts for Service-Level Agreements in Edge-to-Cloud Computing	2020	Journal	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Smart Contract	Experiment > 50%
S18	[7]	Blockchain technologies and microservices for open learning communities. A software architecture perspective	2020	Journal	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Education	Not empirically evaluated
S19	[28]	Hybrid blockchain-enabled secure microservices fabric for decentralized multi-domain avionics systems	2020	Journal	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Aviation Systems	Experiment > 50%
S20	[29]	Hosting virtual IoT resources on edge-hosts with blockchain	2016	Conference	Proposal of solution	System	IoT	Experiment > 50%
S21	[30]	FBaaS: Functional Blockchain as a Service	2018	Conference	Proposal of solution	Model	General	Not empirically evaluated
S22	[31]	Benchmarking Blockchain Interactions in a Mobile Edge Cloud Software Systems	2020	Symposium	Proposal of solution	Framework	General	Experiment > 50%
S23	[32]	A Microservice-enabled Architecture for Smart Surveillance using Blockchain Technology	2018	Conference	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Surveillance Systems	Not empirically evaluated
S24	[33]	EduChain: CIA-Compliant Block-chain for Intelligent Cyber Defense of Microservices in Education Industry 4.0	2021	Journal	Validation research	Framework	Education	Experiment > 50%
S25	[34]	BlendSM-DDM: Blockchain-Enabled Secure Microservices for Decentralized Data Marketplaces	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Online Commerce/Marketplace	Not empirically evaluated
S26	[35]	Implementing a Microservices System with Blockchain Smart Contracts	2019	Workshop	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Healthcare	Case Study < 50%
S27	[36]	Blockchain and off-chain: A Solution for Audit Issues in Supply Chain Systems	2020	Conference	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Supply Chain	Case Study > 50%
S28	[37]	Osmotic Computing: Software Defined Membranes meet Private/Federated Blockchains	2018	Symposium	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Osmotic Computing	Not empirically evaluated
S29	[38]	Novel Vote Scheme for Decision-Making Feedback Based on Blockchain in Internet of Vehicles	2021	Journal	Validation research	Model	IoV	Experiment < 50%
S30	[39]	BFIM: Performance Measurement of a Blockchain Based Hierarchical Tree Layered Fog-IoT Microservice Architecture	2021	Journal	Proposal of solution	Architecture	IoT	Experiment < 50%

		Three Layered IoT/IIoT Microservice Architecture						
S31	[40]	A Microservices-based Virtualized Blockchain Framework for Emerging 5G Data Networks	2019	Workshop	Validation research	Framework	General	Not empirically evaluated
S32	[41]	A Blockchain-based Trustworthy Certification Process for Composite Services	2020	Conference	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Healthcare	Experiment > 50%
S33	[42]	Basic Principles of Osmotic Computing: Secure and Dependable MicroElements (MELs) Orchestration Leveraging Blockchain Facilities	2018	Conference	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Osmotic Computing	Not empirically evaluated
S34	[43]	Tikiri—Towards a lightweight blockchain for IoT	2021	Journal	Validation research	Architecture	IoT	Experiment < 50%
S35	[44]	A blockchain-based trusted edge platform in edge computing environment	2021	Journal	Validation research	Platform	General	Experiment > 50%
S36	[45]	Intelligent microservice based on blockchain for healthcare applications	2021	Journal	Validation research	Architecture	Healthcare	Case Study < 50%
S37	[46]	Adapted smart home services based on smart contracts and service level agreements	2021	Journal	Proposal of solution	Architecture	Healthcare	Case Study < 50%
S38	[47]	Decentralized service registry and discovery in P2P networks using blockchain technology	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	Architecture	General	Not empirically evaluated
S39	[48]	Using blockchain to push software-defined IoT components onto edge hosts	2016	Conference	Validation research	Model	IoT	Experiment < 50%
S40	[49]	Urgent and Emergency Care: An Academic Application System Case Study	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	System	Healthcare	Case Study < 50%